

To estimate field parasitism by the nematode, weekly collections of BPH infesting paddy were made. About half of the BPH collected were dissected; the others were reared in the laboratory. The table shows parasitism.

This Mermithid was also reared from

field collected *Sogatella furcifera* and *Nephotettix nigropictus*.

The Mirid *Cyrtorhinus lividipennis*, an important predator of the BPH, was parasitized by another Mermithid which may represent a new genus. However, it was scarce.

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Occurrence of brown planthopper on rice in West Bengal, India

P. B. Chatterjee, entomologist, Operational Research Project on Integrated Control of Rice Pests, Pandua, Hooghly, West Bengal, India

In West Bengal, the brown planthopper (BPH) *Nilaparvata lugens* was first noted as a serious pest of summer (boro) rice in 1973 at Khanakul, Hooghly district. Epidemics of the pest have since appeared

regularly in ever-larger areas. Recently the infestation has spread to other rice-growing areas of West Bengal, particularly river and coastal belts. The BPH has also been recorded on main winter (kharif or aman) rice, but there damage is less.

The main rice-growing area of Khanakul is low-lying and basinlike; water from two rivers and a number of drainage channels are impounded there. Summer rice is the main crop because land is submerged from July to November.

The initial attack is by immigrant macropterous insects, which produce both macropterous and brachypterous forms, during late February and March. Hopperburn is noticed in April. The pest disappears in mid-May, at the time of rice harvest. All the high yielding photoperiod-insensitive rice varieties are attacked. But some local rice varieties of lower yield potential that are transplanted earlier escape damage.

Populations of leafhoppers and planthoppers in Egypt from 1973 to 1975, as indicated by sweep-net samples

El-Desouky Ammar, Faculty of Agriculture, Cairo University, Cairo Egypt (present address: Department of Biology, Faculty of Education, King Abdul-Aziz University, Mecca, Saudi Arabia); and O. Lamie and I. A. Khodir, Faculty of Agriculture, Kafr-el-Sheikh, Egypt

Samples of leafhoppers and planthoppers were taken weekly with a sweep net (1 00 double strokes/sample) throughout the April to November rice-growing seasons from 1973 to 1975 at Kafr-el-Sheikh, Egypt. Eight cicadellid species, six delphacids, and only one cixiid were found. But two dominant species were caught in great numbers - *Balclutha hortensis* and *Sogatella vibix*. Next in abundance were *Nephotettix modulatus* and *Sogatella furcifera* (see table).

The number of leafhoppers and planthoppers increased gradually from year to year. In the three successive seasons of 1973, 1974, and 1975, cicadellids averaged 44.5, 258.6, and 929.5 insects/100 strokes, respectively; delphacids, 17.3, 271.4, and 623.1/100 strokes. In 1973, populations of most

cicadellids peaked in July and August; in 1974 and 1975, they peaked in October and November. Populations of all the delphacid species, however, peaked

in October and November in the 3 sampling years.

The average sex ratio of various species from 1973 to 1975 was near equality

Population density and sex ratio of leafhoppers and planthoppers in sweep-net samples taken weekly throughout the rice-growing season (Apr.–Nov.) at Kafr-el-Sheikh, Egypt, 1973 to 1975.

Family and species	Mean no./100 strokes			Peak no./100 strokes ^a			Males (av %)
	1973	1974	1975	1973	1974	1975	
FAMILY CICADELLIDAE							
<i>Balclutha hortensis</i>	18.7	238.7	875.4	32.8	807.0	2955.2	46.3
<i>Nephotettix modulatus</i>	6.3	3.2	42.0	14.4	13.8	166.4	54.1
<i>Cicadulina bipunctella</i>							
<i>zeae</i>	9.5	14.7	6.5	19.5	43.3	19.3	46.8
<i>Empoasca decipiens</i>	3.6	0.8	2.8	10.3	3.0	13.8	43.7
<i>Macrostelus sexnotatus</i>	5.5	0.7	1.0	16.0	2.0	3.8	28.7
<i>Exitianus taeniaceps</i>	0.9	0.5	1.3	2.8	1.5	7.3	62.8
<i>Recilia schmidtgeni</i>	0.0	0.0	0.6	—	—	2.7	—
<i>Neoliturus haematoceps</i>	0.0	0.1	0.0	0.0	0.2	0.0	—
Total	44.5	258.6	929.5	86.0	853.0	3136.8	—
FAMILY DELPHACIDAE							
<i>Sogatella vibix</i>	12.8	250.0	593.5	24.0	1400.0	2507.2	54.5
<i>Sogatella furcifera</i>	3.1	19.3	26.6	9.5	116.0	124.4	55.2
<i>Toya nigeriensis</i>	0.9	0.8	2.0	5.0	4.0	5.3	47.9
<i>Falctoya aglauros</i>	0.4	1.3	0.8	3.0	6.0	2.0	75.4
<i>Matutinus iphias</i>	0.0	0.1	0.2	—	—	—	—
<i>Dopidocephala elegans</i>	0.0	0.0	0.2	—	—	—	—
Total	17.3	271.4	623.1	41.5	1526.0	2638.0	—
FAMILY CIXIIDAE							
<i>Oliarus frontalis</i>	0.0	0.1	0.1	0.0	2.0	3.0	75.0

^aMonthly average.

(44–55% males) in most species, but it was far from equality in *Macrosteles sexnotatus* (29% males), *Exitianus taeniaceps* (63% males), and *Falctoya aglauros*, and *Oliarus frontalis* (75% males each). **W**

Control of rice thrips *Baliothrips biformis* with seedling root dip treatments

M. Mohanasundaram, P. V. Subba Rao, and I. P. Janaki, Department of Entomology, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore 641003, India

An experiment conducted at the Paddy Breeding Station, Coimbatore, in kharif 1976 evaluated the effectiveness of selected insecticides as root-dip treatment for controlling pests in newly transplanted rice. The trial was laid out with four insecticides – chlorpyrifos, chlorfenvinphos, dimethoate, and leptophos – at different concentrations and exposure times in a randomized design replicated four times, and

Percentage of leaves affected by thrips at 15 days after transplanting. Coimbatore, India.

Chemical concn (%)	Exposure time (h)	Leaves (%) affected ^a
<i>Chlorpyrifos 20 EC</i>		
0.02	2	14.6
0.02	4	13.9
0.02	12	13.9
0.04	2	12.1
0.4	4	9.6
<i>Chlorfenvinphos 24 EC</i>		
0.02	2	17.3
0.02	4	10.1
0.02	12	14.9
0.04	2	15.2
0.04	4	17.5
<i>Dimethoate 30 EC</i>		
0.02	2	21.5
0.02	4	7.8
0.02	12	13.1
0.04	2	12.8
0.4	4	11.2
<i>Leptophos 35 EC</i>		
0.02	2	10.4
0.02	4	13.0
0.02	12	20.2
0.4	2	17.2
0.04	4	14.9
<i>Control</i>		36.1

^aS.E. = 2.93%; C.D. = 8.64%. Average of four replications.

compared with an untreated control. The seedling roots were kept in the insecticide solutions for specified times before transplanting. Pests such as thrips, whorl maggots, and stem borers on five random plants per replication were recorded at 15,30, and 45 days after transplanting (DT).

All the insecticides significantly reduced thrip incidence at 15 DT. Chlorpyrifos at 0.04% for 4 hours was best, followed by dimethoate at 0.02% for 4 hours, and chlorfenvinphos at

0.02% for 4 hours. The whorl maggot was noticed only at 30 DT, but the incidence was low. However, the incidence was minimum in the chlorfenvinphos 0.02% treatment for 4 hours. In all treatments, stem borer incidence was less than that in the control at 30 DT, but increased by 45 DT. Although not extremely effective, seedling root dip with chlorpyrifos 0.04% or dimethoate 0.02% for 4 hours can be used to control thrips in the early transplanted crop. **W**

Ragged stunt virus disease in India and Sri Lanka

E. A. Heinrichs, entomologist, and G. S. Khush, plant breeder, International Rice Research Institute

During the International Rice Testing Program monitoring tour to South India and Sri Lanka in February 1978, rice plants with symptoms of ragged stunt virus disease—identical to those previously observed in the Philippines, Indonesia, and Thailand—were observed. Numerous TNAU breeding lines at the Paddy Breeding Station, Tamil Nadu Agricultural University, Coimbatore,

India, were infected. At the Batalagoda Central Rice Breeding Station, Sri Lanka; only one plant of the variety BG 34-8 was observed to be infected. Transmission studies will be conducted by Indian and Sri Lankan scientists to confirm the reports.

Recent epidemics in Indonesia and the Philippines have brought ragged stunt to the attention of rice scientists. The presence of the disease in such widely separated geographical regions as Sri Lanka, India, the Philippines, Indonesia, and Thailand indicates that it has probably been endemic in Asia for years. **W**

Pest management and control WEEDS

Effects of herbicides on rice seed coated with activated carbon and direct seeded

W. L. Chang and C. N. Chao, Chiayi Agricultural Experiment Station, Taiwan Agricultural Research Institute, Chiayi, Taiwan

The performance of five granular herbicides in broadcast-flooded rice was evaluated in the second crop of 1977 at the Chiayi Station. Seed of the modem indica selection, Chianung-sen-yu 13 were coated with 8 kg activated carbon/ha before broadcasting on a flooded soil at the rate of 100 kg/ha. Mixed seeds of *Echinochloa crus-galli*, *Monochoria vaginalis*, and *Cyperus difformis* were also

sown at 3 kg/ha immediately after the rice seed were broadcast. Herbicides were applied at 6 days after seeding, when most of the rice and weeds were at the one- to two-leaf stage.

Of the five granular herbicides (see table), Perfluidone/2,4-D IPE gave the best weed control. Benzglycereth (WL29226) gave the poorest control; the others controlled weeds satisfactorily. Coating rice seeds with activated carbon did not affect the effectiveness of herbicides, but it improved their selectivity to direct-seeded rice considerably. When activated carbon was used, rice toxicity ratings were reduced by almost a third in the less selective granular herbicides terbuchlor,